

II- IPT Conference Proceedings

Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule (ETH)
Zürich, 2024

International Physicists' Tournament

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by

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Preface by our president

Dear IPT Community,

it became a good tradition to gather the solutions of the IPT problems, have fun and stimulating discussion at the IPT Conference and publish the book of abstracts. We know very clearly how much efforts and enthusiasm you guys are putting into solving the problems, running the experiments, analysing hours of videos, deriving monstrous equations. This all makes the IPT a unique learning experience. This book of abstracts is another way from us to give your efforts an academic weight, and to give you a safe space for working on it - for some of our participants, the IPT Conference may be their first experience of conference participation. I am grateful to all the contributors who filled the book with their diverse contributions. See you next year!

All the best,

Anastasiia Vasylychenkova
President of the IPT
November 2025

A word to the students

Dear IPT participants,

Welcome to the second edition of the Conference Proceedings of the IPT! This year we had a record of participation at the conference, which reflects also the number of abstracts that were included here. When we first started the conference, we had no idea how big it would become, but it shows the dedication and passion for solving very peculiar physics problems such as building a galton board, determining how good a cachaça is through sound (a trick that even being Brazilian I did not know of), or predicting the which egg will win an egg fight (also one of the curious things I learned this year). Thanks a lot for all contributions!

Matheus Azevedo Silva Pessoa
Editor of the IPT Conference Proceedings and
Member of the Executive Committee of the IPT
November 2025

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The IPT Problems

During the competition, we saw solutions of all 17 IPT problems. In these proceedings, we present abstracts from 10 of these problems, which are listed below.

Galton board

Dropping a set of beads on a board with evenly distributed pegs results in a binomial distribution. Is it possible to generate other kinds of distributions by varying some parameters (pegs size, pegs distribution, bead format, etc.)? Is it possible to achieve a distribution that does not obey the central limit theorem in an i.i.d. scenario? What happens to the distribution when one makes the board vibrate?

Jumpy Hoop

Given enough angular momentum, a hoop with a mass attached to it may demonstrate a jumping motion when it is rolling. Explain the phenomenon and how it depends on the relevant parameters. Is it possible to reproduce this behavior with any unbalanced mass distribution on a wheel? What happens when one changes the profile of the ground? Can you add a mechanical contraption (that will not touch the ground) to the hoop to increase the maximal height of the jump?

Solenoid Resonance

Consider a helicoidal spring hanging vertically with a mass attached to it as a solenoid. If one lets current flow through the spring, it creates a magnetic field. How can one influence the motion of the spring by changing this current? What happens if we put this system in an RLC circuit (where L is our spring) with AC current? What kind of resonant phenomena and energy transfer between the mechanical and electromagnetic modes can be achieved?

Alcohol sound check

Some distilleries in Brazil praise their product's quality by the distinct sound it makes when the bottle is hit after being quickly turned upside down. Investigate the phenomenon. Why does the effect not work with alcoholic carbonated drinks? What other liquids will maintain this "damping" effect for longer?

PVC cement droplets

PVC cement is a material used in plumbing to solder PVC pipes together. PVC cement droplets have been observed to spin when dropped in water. Explain the physical mechanisms that cause the peculiar motion of the droplets. Study how the shape of the droplets impacts their rotation. Can you create droplets that propel across the water instead of rotating? Maximize their rotational and translational motion.

Salty shapes

In some deserts, such as Death Valley, one can see salt polygons that have formed through the evaporation of salty water. Investigate and explain the phenomenon. Reproduce the phenomenon in the lab. Which two dimensional pattern can one obtain in such an experiment? What is the size of the smallest polygon you can obtain?

Peculiar echo

The combination of a clap and the massive pyramid (Chichen Itza, Mexico) gives rise to a mysterious sound called "Quetzal tail", as shown in the video. Investigate the phenomenon, find the necessary conditions to create it, and reproduce it.

The bright spot

There is a famous phenomenon in wave optics called the Arago-Poisson spot where a bright spot is created in the middle of the shadow of a spherical object when one shines coherent light on it. By shining the light on other types of solids (e.g. cubes, cylinders, etc.) one gets different patterns to appear in the shadow of the object. What information about the geometry of a solid can be obtained by analyzing the pattern in its shadow?

Egg fight

Egg tapping is a traditional game where two players hold a boiled egg. Each player hits the other player's egg with their own, as shown in the video. The player whose egg has cracked loses the game. Devise a non-invasive method to predict the winning egg among the given two. Improve the prediction with invasive examination methods.

Unrolling tape

When unrolling a roll of adhesive tape, a loud sound can be produced. Explain the physics of the sound emission. Find ways to maximize and minimize the noise.

Anti-bubbles

Fill a container with water with decreased surface tension. Then drop a droplet of regular water into the container (very slowly). The droplet will create a so-called "anti-bubble". Investigate the phenomenon. Maximize the size and lifetime of an anti-bubble. Are these quantities related?

1

Exploring the Boundaries of the Central Limit Theorem: An Experimental and Theoretical Investigation of the Galton Board

**Iason Kazazis,
Greece**

The Galton board is a simple yet effective device that demonstrates how the Central Limit Theorem applies to a physical system and allows for the visualization of discrete probability distributions, such as the binomial distribution, which approximates the normal distribution. This work investigates the physical parameters of the board that determine the final distribution of the beads, aiming to generate non-normal distributions. We focus on the features of the distributions in order to examine if the Central Limit Theorem applies when certain conditions are met. We further explore the effects of a vibrating board. In order to study the motion of the objects on the board, an original, problem-specific notation has been developed based on the random walk stochastic process. Two different experimental setups were constructed to perform tests with changing variables and a vibrating motion which were compared to numerical simulation results. The experimental and theoretical results as well as future study prospects are discussed.

2

Non-gaussian Controllable Galton Board Distributions through Modelling with a Single Metaparameter

**Griffin Hiscoke,
Sweden**

To statistically observe the resulting distribution of balls dropping through a non-ideal Galton Board, the underlying mechanical processes must be modelled and approximated. This study proposes a parameter which summarises the effects of a range of factors such as elasticity, shapes, spacings and sizes, and allows for fast determination of the resulting distribution. This is done by considering the probability of a ball continuing to move in the same direction when it descends a layer and hits a peg. The parameter, and by extension the behaviour of the full board, can be measured by conducting a low number of experiments on a subset of the board consisting of only 3 pegs.

The simplification is then applied to model a real-world board and used to generate non-uniform peg distributions which provide controllable non-gaussian resulting distributions. Physical experiments show the model to have a smaller inaccuracy than the human error caused by placing pegs by hand. Although the parameter depends on a wide range of properties, we elected to vary it through changing the horizontal spacing between peg columns.

Further studies would include exploring the limits of the simplification, as well as reducing human error in constructing physical boards. Additional experiments could allow for predicting the parameter value for different board parameters without conducting experiments on the specific board.

3

Solution of the Galton board problem with three different approaches

Borna Stjepić,
Croatia

We have solved the Galton board problem using three different methods, mathematical approach, Hamiltonian approach and diffusion approach and experimentally verified our data.

4

Jumpy Hoop

**Seyedeh Zahra Hosseini,
Iran**

This study investigates the phenomenon of a hoop with an attached mass exhibiting a jumping motion when rolling with sufficient angular momentum. It is explained by the interplay of angular momentum, gravitational force, and the rotational dynamics of the system. Key parameters influencing this behavior include the mass of the hoop, the attached mass, and the initial angular velocity. The study explores whether similar behavior can be reproduced with alternative unbalanced mass distributions on a wheel and discusses the implications of varying ground profiles on the jumping motion. Results show the specific dynamics depend on the distribution and magnitude of the mass. Changes in ground profile are found to alter the trajectory and characteristics of the jumping motion and highlighting the importance of environmental factors in such dynamic systems. In our study, we explored the impact of three distinct hoop materials - metal, plastic, and wood - on the dynamics of a jumping motion. Alongside material variation, we investigated the influence of hoop size and the mass attached to the hoop. Through experimental analysis, this article elucidates how these parameters shape the jumping phenomenon. By examining the experimental results, the analysis of the results presented in this study utilized COMSOL for simulation purposes, with MATLAB employed for generating phase diagrams. Additionally, TRACKER software facilitated the numerical analysis, particularly in determining the jump angle. By leveraging these tools, we were able to comprehensively examine the experimental data and draw the conclusions regarding the influence of hoop material, size variations, and attached mass on the dynamics of the jumping motion [1, 2, 3].

5

Probing the motions of a spring under current

Alexandros Desylas,
Greece

The solenoid is an electromagnet constructed by a helical coil of conductive wire. By attaching a mass to a vertically hanging solenoid which is part of a DC current circuit, one can convert it into a mechanical oscillator and study the interaction between the electromagnetic and mechanical systems. We modeled this interaction with a non-linear second order ordinary differential equation which we solved both analytically and numerically. Additionally, we analyzed the behavior of an RLC system with a spring as the inductor and investigated the dependency of the spring's motion to the relevant parameters. Also, the energy transfer between the mechanical and the electromagnetic system was investigated. Finally, our theoretical models were confirmed by the experiments that we conducted.

6

Qualifying the Damped Oscillation of Acoustic Bubbles.

**Penelope Pouli,
Canada**

The study of acoustic interactions between sound fields and bubbles has diverse applications in medicine, engineering, and biology, including optimizing ultrasound imaging, reducing watercraft damage, and advancing our understanding of aquatic animal biology. The study of sound-bubble interactions also provides a flexible tool since bubbles can be modeled using various theoretical frameworks, such as a simple harmonic oscillator. Our investigation focuses on modeling vibrating bubbles in various liquids as harmonic oscillators. Our research is motivated by a common Brazilian practice used to assess alcohol content, where the sound of a partially filled bottle being struck changes if the bottle is quickly inverted beforehand. This distinct sound results from the liquid's state, particularly the bubbles formed within it. Specifically, this sound difference can be attributed to the damped oscillations of the induced bubbles in the viscous liquid. We recorded the sound spectrum before and after the rotation to compare peak frequencies. Liquids were categorized based on how long they maintained the sound difference, quantifying the damping phenomenon using quality factors from a Lorentzian fit of the sound spectrum. This established a direct relationship between the oscillation's period and amplitude and the liquid's properties. Results indicated that as viscosity increases, the quality factor decreases, reducing bubble vibrations and causing the sound difference to fade more quickly. This study highlighted the role of viscous damping as a sound attenuator and successfully demonstrated the relationship between emitted frequencies in different beverages, enhancing our understanding of bubble dynamics.

7

Experiment and simulation of damping in alcohol solutions

**Nicolai Christian Kongstad,
Denmark**

When alcohol solutions in bottles are aerated their sound when hit will be damped. In this presentation this phenomenon is investigated. Experiments on different alcohol solutions and other liquids have been done to show the effect and to investigate how viscosity changes the damping. To explain the phenomenon, theory will be presented which, when combined with FEM simulations, explain the damping.

Tuning into Spirits: The Sound of Quality Liquor

**Lucas de Alexandri Dantas Heck,
Brazil**

In the 2024 International Physics Tournament (IPT), Problem number 4 titled "Alcoholic Sound Check" prompts participants to explore the phenomenon of a distinct sound occurring when a bottle of liquor is struck after being quickly turned upside down. Through the investigation, it became evident that this effect is attributed to the presence of bubbles within the liquid. This revelation underscores the significance of both bottle properties, which influence the base frequencies of sound, and liquid properties such as density, viscosity, and surface tension in understanding the phenomenon. The study introduces a visual method for measuring the distribution of bubbles over time, complemented by simulations and theoretical frameworks that align with observed patterns. This comprehensive approach contributes to a deeper understanding of the underlying physics and aids in elucidating the factors governing the observed sound phenomenon in alcoholic beverages.

9

Formation of PVC cement droplets

**William Castillo Cabrera,
Mexico**

When drops of PVC cement are deposited on water, they will start spinning with chaotic movement. To characterize this phenomenon, we used different methods leading to the conclusion of water tension being the main reason. Therefore, when the solvents of the cement evaporate, between the tension layer and the surface of the PVC droplet, there is an accumulation of solvent that ends breaking up thus leading to the chaotic movement.

Figure 9.1: Experimental images of the formation of different types of PVC cement droplets, in blue for higher contrast.

10

Salty shapes and Swiss cheese

**Mateusz Winiarski, Wiktor Zantowicz,
Poland (Krakow)**

It is known, that salty shapes create pattern known as Voronoi shapes. In our presentation, we will show a Voronoi-like pattern inspired by Swiss cheese, that matches provided theory as well as results seen in nature.

11

A theoretical model for the echo from the Chichen Itza pyramid

**Bruno Siqueira Eduardo,
Brazil**

When one claps in front of the Chichen Itza pyramid, an interesting echo is generated. After the investigation of some qualitative aspects of the phenomenon, we were able to isolate the most important parameters that contribute to the resultant sound. They motivated a set of reasonable assumptions to the problem, allowing the development of a theoretical model whose inputs are solely the duration of the clap, the speed of sound, the distance to the pyramid and the geometry of its main staircase. The output of the model is a simple analytical expression that accurately reproduces the "peculiar" features present in the spectrogram of the echo, with no need to fit any parameters.

12

Echoes from staircases calculation by convolution-scattering

**Ivan Prearo,
Brazil**

The peculiar echo produced by the El Castillo pyramid has been studied and reproduced both mathematical and experimentally in situ. The main cause of the echo was found to be the geometry of an observer clapping their hands at a reasonable distance of the bottom of the pyramid. Two modelling approaches give very similar results in accuracy with different degrees of detail: construction interference between echos from consecutive steps; and the staircase as a diffraction grid with varying step sizes. The echo effect was observable in 4 separate UNICAMP staircases, which were measured and had their echoes calculated using a convolution-scattering model [1] in order to compare experiments and theory. The frequency spectrum found from the models agreed with the acquired experimental data. Using the construction interference model, it is possible to have a rough first estimate for the frequency curve for the echo of any staircase. This was used to verify the possibility of a lab-scale experiment, with millimeter-sized steps. Since the frequencies found were in the order of 115kHz, way above the human hearing limits, this experiment was discarded [4].

13

The Enigma of the Chirping Echo: Unveiling the Acoustics of Chichen Itza's Pyramid

**Amin Reza Mahmoodi, Mahan Fallahpour, Seyedeh Zahra Hosseini,
Iran**

In this research the intriguing phenomenon of the "chirping echo" produced by the Great Pyramid of Chichen Itza, is investigated. When a clap resonates against the structure's steps, a sound akin to a quetzal bird's call emerges. By meticulous diffraction simulations, the research tackles the question of how the architectural design of the pyramid shapes the echo into a series of chirps. The repetitive pitch phenomenon analysis reveals a critical finding: the frequency of the returning sound is independent of the initial clap and instead, it is entirely due to the intricate geometric configuration of the pyramid itself. Two prominent models are used to explain this fascinating acoustic interaction: the Lubman torsional scattering model and the Declercq diffraction model. The Lubman model depicts the clap-echo process as a linear system that remains constant over time. However, its results indicate a dependence of the echo on the random spectrum of the initial sound, which contradicts the observed independence of frequency from the source. In contrast, the Declercq diffraction model offers a more compelling explanation. It assumes that the tiered steps of the pyramid act as a diffraction grating, selectively scattering the sound waves generated by the clap. This selective scattering, based on the wavelength of the sound, leads to a specific pattern of echoes arriving at the listener's ears at slightly different intervals. The human brain perceives these rapid, periodic variations in arrival time as a change in pitch, creating the characteristic chirping effect. Examining and comparing these models by meticulous simulations result in a more comprehensive understanding of the acoustic marvels embedded within the architecture of Chichen Itza. This research not only contributes to the field of acoustic engineering but also offers valuable insights into the potential role the acoustic considerations may have played in the design and construction of this ancient Mayan monument [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

14

Decoding Shadows

**Vinícius dos Passos de Souza,
Brazil**

Understanding a 3D object's geometry solely by observing its shadow pattern presents a challenging problem in computer vision and optical imaging. In this study, we investigate the feasibility of defining object geometry using Fourier optics principles. Through experiments and computational simulations, we demonstrate that Fourier optics provides a powerful framework for extracting geometric information from shadow patterns. Specifically, we present results showing the successful determination of the length of a cylinder and the radius of a sphere based on their respective shadow patterns.

15

Poisson spot

Wiktor Kalinowski, Michał Puza
Poland

Poisson spot is a phenomenon known for 200 years that was crucial in understanding and proving wave properties of light. We approached this well known physics with modern optical techniques and investigated if we can retrieve some geometrical information from diffraction pattern in the shadow. We used Gerchberg-Saxon phase retrieval algorithm to determine the shape of the object casting shadow and succeeded in using it in experiment.

16

A geometric approach to diffraction

**Filippos Typas,
Greece**

A spherical object illuminated by coherent light produces a bright spot in the center of its shadow, known as the Arago-Poisson-Fresnel spot. By shining monochromatic light on solids of various shapes, unique patterns emerge in the shadow region. The purpose of this presentation is to examine the geometric connection of those patterns with the obstacles from which they were formed. Theory extends from the usage of the Fresnel approximation integral to the line integral method and the evolute approach to diffraction. Solids of small dimensions are compared to their corresponding 2D plane projection blocks and were found to provide very similar results in the shadow region, when normal incidence in the Fresnel region is taken into account. Specifically, a metallic tilted cylinder was contrasted to a metallic sheet of the same dimensions, with both resulting in the same diffraction pattern. Intensity graphs of a sphere, a disk and a cylinder of the same cross section were obtained and presented the same diffraction characteristics. Evolute theory is employed on ellipses of increased eccentricity resulting in predominant, bright stretched asteroids with a complex inner structure. Semi-cubical parabolas formed by parabolas, Inverse cardioids from cardioid blocks, evolutes corresponding to a variety of other obstacles are depicted with great accuracy. All in all, we successfully merged different theoretical approaches to observations and matched 3D objects to their 2D projections.

17

The Bright Spot

**Oscar Ernesto Angulo Flores,
Mexico**

The essential framework for understanding the diffraction phenomenon is presented, which is used to explain the peculiar diffraction patterns that appear in the shadows of different objects. A simulation is used to see these results.

Study of the Arago-Poisson spot

Viktor Sundstrom,
Sweden

The Arago-Poisson spot is a diffractive phenomena typically associated with the early experiments verifying the wave like nature of light. This study has investigated diffraction in the context of the Arago-Poisson spot. Theoretical and experimental results suggest that for simple shapes, the two-dimensional projected area of a three-dimensional shape is sufficient to determine its diffractive shadow. Based on this observation, a simplified two dimensional model centered around Huygen sources originating from the edges of a shape was proposed. This model was verified with simulations using the Rayleigh-Sommerfeld integral and experimental data. The diffractive pattern of simulations and experiments were reversed using the Hybrid Input Output and Error Reduction phase retrieval algorithm implemented by the Python package Pyphase (HIO-ER). The simplified model was able to predict general features of the diffraction patterns of the shadow. This information could be used to construct an algorithm which reverses the shape of an object based on such general features. HIO-ER was able to reverse the contours of simulated diffraction patterns with high precision but was not as successful with the experimental data. This study identifies the quality of the experimental data as the main reason for this and the HIO-ER is thought to be able to reverse experimental data from a more refined setup.

Figure 18.1: Left: Diffraction pattern of heart predicted from simplified model. Center: Heart propagated using simulations. Right: Reversal of heart diffraction pattern using HIO-ER.

19

Crack Conundrum: Exploring Factors Influencing Success in the Traditional Game of 'Egg Tapping'

**Mahan Fallahpour, Amin Reza Mahmoodi, Seyedeh Zahra Hosseini,
Iran**

In this research, the influential factors determining the prediction of the winning egg in the traditional game of "egg tapping" are investigated. Egg tapping is a traditional and entertaining game in which two players attempt to break each other's boiled eggs by tapping them together. Predicting the winning egg in this game has been a subject of interest for a long time. The key parameters affecting this phenomenon are geometric hardness, the force required to break the egg, the internal structure, and the effect of the cooking method. The study categorizes these factors into three primary domains. Firstly, eggshell-related factors such as geometric hardness and stress in the shell are examined, significantly impacting the egg's resilience during the game. Secondly, the internal structure of the egg is scrutinized to understand its role in enhancing or weakening resistance against impact-induced fractures. This structural analysis contributes to a better understanding of the game's mechanics. Finally, the method and conditions of force application onto the egg surface are explored. Additionally, the study investigates the influence of various egg-cooking methods on fracture resistance. This investigation provides valuable insights into the interaction between material integrity and culinary practices, facilitating a deeper understanding of influential factors in "egg tapping". This aids in better predicting winning eggs and enhances comprehension of egg structure and physics at the surface level. [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]

20

Egg Fight Predictions: A Resonant Frequency Analysis method to determine the winner of an egg fight

**Angelopoulou Eleni-Amaranta,
Greece**

Egg tapping is a traditional game where two players hold a boiled egg. Each player hits the other player's egg with their own. The player whose egg cracks loses the game. The main theoretical focus of our research was to evaluate the quality of the two chosen eggs by taking advantage of a signature frequency produced as a vibrational response of the egg after being mechanically excited. A large experimental data set was analyzed to assess the accuracy of our model, concluding that the winning egg can be predicted this way with an 85 % rate of success.

21

Sound analysis of unrolling tape

**Anna Krasynikova,
Ukraine**

Let us consider a roll of adhesive tape. While it is unrolled tape produces a loud sound. We tested and confirmed the hypothesis about what was the reason of sound emission and made an investigation for minimizing and maximizing of amplitude of emitted sound.

22

Preliminary investigations into surface anti-bubbles

**Malli Segoli,
Denmark**

In this presentation preliminary investigations into surface anti-bubbles are presented. The anti-bubble does not break through the soapy water surface, but lies on top with a thin layer of air in between the bubble and surface, when the bubble lands 'slowly' on the surface. Air cushioning and polarity is suggested as possible explanations for the phenomenon. Varying the soap concentration gave inconclusive trends in lifetime. However it was found, that food colouring significantly prolongs the lifetime when dripping antibubbles onto a pure water surface. Different sizes of bubbles can be achieved by using different pipettes, using a 'soft jet', merging or splitting bubbles. Small offshoots of bubbles, moving across the surface, had a comparatively longer lifetime, while lifetime variation of bubbles created by 'soft jet' was inconclusive. Longer lifetimes of above one minute were achieved by vibrating the surface or replacing air with oil in the interface. Finally suggestions for further investigations are presented.

23

Anti-bubbles formation and lifetime

**Daryna Sych,
Ukraine**

An anti-bubble is a droplet of liquid surrounded by a thin film of gas, as opposed to a gas bubble, which is a sphere of gas surrounded by a liquid. A model of formation and lifetime of the anti-bubbles is proposed. The lifetime of an anti-bubble is determined by thinning of air layer. We show that the lifetime of anti-bubbles is dependant on surface tension and temperature. In the experiment, we investigate the relation between lifetime and size of antibubbles.

24

Egg Fight

**Matvei Anoshin,
Team IPT**

To predict the winner of a given egg fight, a non-invasive evaluation pipeline has been developed that includes size measurement, acoustic determination of the eggshell's eigenfrequency, and ovoscopy for precise analysis of the eggshell surface. After the pipeline is completed, the egg is boiled and then knocked against another one. Then, the radius of curvature at the contact point is derived from the contact angle and an approximated egg shape. These data, along with COMSOL simulations, allow to estimate the egg's Young's modulus from its eigenfrequency, thereby providing all required information to describe an egg fight as a process of stress distribution between shells until one breaks due to reaching the maximum pressure caused by the buckling effect.

Final prediction was performed using both supervised and unsupervised approaches. In the unsupervised approach, the eggshell strength function $\sigma_{crit}(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{r}, \dots)$ was expanded into a Taylor series and then optimized as a multivariate function. For the supervised approach, the Gaussian Naive Bayes algorithm was used due to the independence of the measured properties and their approximately normal distribution. These techniques resulted in a non-invasive winner prediction accuracy of 88.8%. After including the invasively measured eggshell thickness, the prediction accuracy increased to 91%.

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